

THE ROLE OF SUBTITLES IN TEACHING ESL IN MODERN WORLD

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The purpose of the thesis is to investigate how dual subtitles impact the listening comprehension and vocabulary learning of beginner-level learners and demonstrate how language learning tools can be utilized in and out of ESL classrooms. A review of the literature includes a historical overview of the benefits of using different subtitling conditions; the effect of different subtitling conditions and the level of learners on vocabulary learning and listening comprehension. The following are the most typical forms of film subtitles (Kanellopoulou et al., 2019):

1. L2 audio with L1 subtitles (standard subtitling),
2. L2 audio with L2 captions (bimodal/captions),
3. L2 audio without subtitles (no subtitling/zero captions),
4. L1 audio with L2 subtitles (reserved subtitles).

Besides there is another form called dual subtitles which means L2 audio with both L1 and L2 captions.

Since utilizing different subtitling conditions is one of the most accessible ways of learning a foreign language, a lot of studies have been carried out to get the most out of this method. It is mentioned that standard and bimodal subtitling, as well as the usage of diverse multimedia, had a good influence on students' auditory and lexical abilities, with standard subtitling being more effective than bimodal subtitling in Hsien's research of 107 English as a foreign language (EFL) students in Taiwan (2015). Moreover, some researchers have found that standard subtitles are helpful for vocabulary learning in experiments comparing standard subtitles with no subtitles (Bellalem (2018), Aidinlou (2016), Hsien (2015)). Liao et al (2020) added the idea of bilingual subtitles to be more useful than no subtitles since they

contributed language assistance to make the content simpler to understand and made it easier to learn. Several types of research have been done in this area throughout the world, however, very few studies were carried out about the use of subtitles in ESL classrooms not only in Uzbekistan but in Central Asia.

2.1. The effect of different subtitling conditions on vocabulary learning and listening comprehension

According to Zanon (2006), there are two common disadvantages of utilizing subtitles in teaching a foreign language. One is a focus on reading that is so intense that the dialogues are neglected or forgotten. The second issue is the trouble of changing the routine of reading once students have become accustomed to it. In addition, a study conducted in one of the Japanese universities to understand the effect of using dual subtitles on vocabulary and listening comprehension indicates that the use of them increased the performance level of the students. Lwo and Lin (2012) pointed out that the higher the level of the students, the more positively it influenced their reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition. In spite of it, he concluded that neither listening comprehension nor vocabulary learning was improved while utilizing L1 or L2 captions. In order to see if proficient and less competent learners differed considerably in their L2 acquisition, in the study the participants were offered two languages from two separate language families on the screen concurrently with captions. The final experiment in the study resulted in the followings: firstly, lower-level learners performed better in particular grammar structures with dual captions than without any captions. Second, with L1 subtitles the participants demonstrated better performance in vocabulary and grammar, but in reading and listening L2 captions assisted to comprehend more. Third, in the test that required students to "translate into L1," the group with L1 subtitles did the highest, followed by the group with dual captions; the group with L2 captions scored the lowest. Fourth, when asked to "repeat in English," the findings of the low-ability group revealed that those with dual captions outperformed those without captions (Lwo and Lin, 2012). It can be concluded that dual subtitles and L1 captions can help students increase their performance. Another study that supports the idea is by

Raine (2013) who examined the use of four subtitling circumstances (L1 Japanese subtitles, L2 English captioned, dual subtitles, and no subtitles) among four groups of students of the university, separately within one of the viewing conditions. Subjects in the study viewed a TED talk video and completed vocabulary tests to assess whether they improved their language skills. The findings showed that the majority of the participants did not improve their vocabulary levels, implying that dual subtitles might not always improve vocabulary acquisition to the same extent as other subtitling situations.

Although the previous studies found several disadvantages and no drastic progress in language acquisition, later Frumuselu et al. (2015) documented that L2 captions assisted students to outperform those who watched videos with L1 subtitles, regardless of their level in L2. Also, according to Bianchi and Ciabattoni (2018), beginner learners find native subtitles more beneficial, while more advanced learners benefited more from L2. One of the recent studies conducted at a university in Kosova (Sadiku, 2018) reports that students watching movies with subtitles outperformed the ones who watched with no subtitles in vocabulary acquisition. Interestingly, English subtitles are more inclined to aid learners in improving their level of recognition, whilst Albanian subtitles are more inclined to aid learners in improving their level of output (Sadiku, 2018). Sadiku summarized that students who watched subtitled films in purposeful learning environments retained the words for three weeks longer than those who watched them in incidental learning environments. However, the participants in this study were different-level learners, therefore, the results may have varied if the level of the learners was low or high only. For example, Wang (2019) clarified that participants' performances differ substantially among subtitles and class grades. In his study, he pointed out that students with L1, L2, and dual subtitles excelled over students without subtitles in vocabulary and comprehension at all levels. The effects of L1, L2, and dual captions on vocabulary acquisition and perception produced mixed results. In Baranowska's (2020) project, 63 Polish intermediate English learners watched a film clip and then answered a set of questions, completed a vocabulary knowledge test, and completed

a self-reported cognitive load survey. They were split into three categories those who saw the clip with L1, those who viewed it with L2, and zero captions. The results show that L2 subtitles help learners acquire vocabulary better than L1 subtitles. Furthermore, Pujadas and Munoz's (2020) observation also supports subtitles and captions to be beneficial. In their study, four classes of secondary school students during eight months watched 24 episodes of a TV series, two of the classes with L2 and the other two with L1 subtitles. The results of the study state that L1 subtitles helped to understand the content, whilst L2 captions facilitated vocabulary acquisition. It means that there are some contradictory conclusions when it comes to vocabulary acquisition and listening comprehension and their relationship with different subtitling conditions, therefore, they should be applied based on the needs of the learners.

References:

1. Bellalem, F.; Neddar, B.A.; Bouagada, H.; Benelhadj Djelloul, D. The Use of Subtitled Movies for Vocabulary Acquisition in ESP Settings: Insights from an Experimental Study in Algeria. *Arab World Engl. J.* 2018, 9, 14.
2. Hsien, C.-H. The Study of DVD Subtitle on EFL Students' English Listening Comprehension and Vocabulary Acquisition. *Int. J. Humanit. Soc. Stud.* 2015, 3, 131–138.
3. Liao, Sixin & Kruger, Jan-Louis & Doherty, Stephen. (2020). The impact of monolingual and bilingual subtitles on visual attention, cognitive load, and comprehension. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*.
4. Lwo, L. and Chia-Tzu Lin, M. (2012). The effects of captions in teenagers' multimedia L2 learning. *ReCALL*, [online] 24(2), pp.188–208. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0958344012000067>
5. Pujadas, G. and Muñoz, C. (2019). Extensive viewing of captioned and subtitled TV series: a study of L2 vocabulary learning by adolescents. *The Language Learning Journal*, 47(4), pp.479–496. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2019.1616806>.

6. Raine, P., 2012. Incidental learning of vocabulary through subtitled authentic videos. *JALT-The Japan Association for Language Teaching*.
7. Wang, Y. (Tina) (2019). Effects of L1/L2 Captioned TV Programs on Students' Vocabulary Learning and Comprehension. *CALICO Journal*, 36(3), pp.204–224. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1558/cj.36268>.